

JEL F21, F23
 DOI 10.5281/zenodo.2549820

THE CONSEQUENCES OF A GLOBAL DIGITALIZATION IN THE PRIVATE CAPITAL MANAGEMENT

S. Apalkov

Oles Honchar Dnipro National University, Dnipro, Ukraine

S. Apalkov. The consequences of a global digitalization in the private capital management. In the article the authors examine the economic essence of the concept of "private capital management" and the consequences of the impact of digital innovations on it. The fundamental changes are taking place in the financial services sector and the FinTech segment is feeding these transformations. Volatile markets, growth of assets under management, increasing competition from nonbanking institutions, creation of new business models form the key drivers for transformation of private banking and wealth management industry.

Keywords: private banking, wealth management, automated investment consulting, alternative finance, digital technologies

In the era of global digital transformations, the success of economic development is largely determined by how effectively private capital management is organized. The use of private investments, including international ones, ensures the inflow of capital into free business stimulating the economic development of any country. The growing competition in the world market for the management of large private capital forces investment banks and other participants to seek innovative ways and strategies to attract and retain wealthy customers. Understanding of how the development of digital technology affects private capital management and what changes should be expected in the market for these services in the future is an important and urgent problem.

Analysis of recent researches and publications

Historically, the institution of private wealth management originated in England and Switzerland, as far back as the 18th century, and therefore, mainly European, and then, American scientists and economists carried out researches in this field. Among them we can distinguish: Markowitz H. [1], Smith, K. V. and Goudzwaard M. B. [2], Merton, R. [3], Maud D. [4], Molyneux Ph. and Omarini A. [5] as well as many others. In Ukraine, one of the leading bankers Aleksandrov O. [6] actively studied this problem. Works of Vallée B. [7], Kerhor Y. [8] and others can be listed among recent studies of French scientists.

Even though the private capital management industry has a century-old history, under the recent active influence of digital transformations, it undergoes fundamental changes and requires new rethinking and approaches. In this regard, the aim of the article is to study the latest trends in the world market of the large private capital management and identify of innovative directions for its development.

The main part

Private capital management

Private capital management (Private Banking) is a complex of the services provided by credit institutions to well-grounded citizens for saving and enhancement of their capital. In fact, it is a financial mosaic which the client makes together with the personal manager to find the personal solution.

The traditional segment nomenclature familiar to most wealth management institutions divides the client base into categories based on private wealth holdings [9]: 1) ultra-high net worth (UHNW); 2) upper high net worth (upper HNW); 3) lower high net worth (lower HNW); 4) affluent (fig. 1).

Fig. 1. The standards for the "client portrait" in private banking

Global private wealth grew by 5.2% in 2015 and reached \$168 trillions. The largest shares belong to North America (36%) and Western Europe (24.5%), however, the Asia-Pacific region is actively increasing its turnover and takes the third place (20.5%) [9]. In general, according to forecasts, the global amount of private wealth for the next 5 years will grow at a rate of 6% per year and reach \$224 trillions by 2020.

Table 1. Global private financial wealth by region

Region	Value, \$ trillions				Growth, %			Share of the region, %			
	2013	2014	2015	2020*	2014/2013	2015/2014	2020/2015	2013	2014	2015	2020*
World	148	160	168	224	7.5%	5.2%	33.5%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%
North America	55.7	59.3	60.4	76	6.5%	1.9%	25.8%	37.5%	37.2%	36.0%	33.9%
Western Europe	36.9	39.1	40.8	48.7	6.0%	4.3%	19.4%	24.9%	24.5%	24.3%	21.7%
Eastern Europe	3.1	3.4	3.6	5.3	9.7%	5.9%	47.2%	2.1%	2.1%	2.1%	2.4%
Japan	12.7	13.1	13.6	15.3	3.1%	3.8%	12.5%	8.6%	8.2%	8.1%	6.8%
Latin America	4.2	4.5	4.8	7.1	7.1%	6.7%	47.9%	2.8%	2.8%	2.9%	3.2%
Middle East and Africa	7.5	7.8	8	11.8	4.0%	2.6%	47.5%	5.1%	4.9%	4.8%	5.3%
Asian-Pacific Area	28.3	32.3	36.6	59.8	14.1%	13.3%	63.4%	19.1%	20.3%	21.8%	26.7%

* forecasted

Source: Compiled by the author according to materials [9]

The volume of private capital funds in offshore centers increased in 2015 by 3% – to \$10 trillion. Growth is due to the activity of customers from emerging markets. Singapore and Hong Kong show the highest increase: + 10%. The countries in North America, Western Europe and Japan, on the contrary, display a decrease of 3%.

UBS (Switzerland), Bank of America Merrill Lynch (USA), Morgan Stanley (USA) and Credit Suisse (Switzerland) play a key role in the private wealth management market. TOP 25 private banks worldwide by assets under management includes three French institutions – BNP Paribas (9 rank), Credit Agricole (22) and CIC (25) (tab. 2).

Table 2. Top 25 private banks worldwide by assets under management (AUM)

Global Ranking	Institution	Country	AUM, USD bln (2015)	Growth, % 2015/2014
1	2	3	4	5
1	UBS	Switzerland	1 737.5	-1.0%
2	Bank of America Merrill Lynch	USA	1 444.8	-2.1%
3	Morgan Stanley	USA	687.3	-53.6%
4	Credit Suisse	Switzerland	620.9	-16.2%
5	Royal Bank of Canada	Canada	508.5	-27.8%
6	Citi	USA	437.0	-20.6%
7	JP Morgan	USA	369.0	-13.8%
8	Goldman Sachs	USA	357.3	-1.6%
9	BNP Paribas	France	311.4	-16.8%
10	Deutsche Bank	Germany	297.5	-11.0%
11	Julius Baer	Switzerland	287.0	-0.8%
12	BMO Financial Group	Canada	261.0	-20.0%
13	HSBC	UK	261.0	-5.1%
14	Pictet	Switzerland	239.2	0.3%
15	Northern Trust	USA	227.3	1.2%
16	Wells Fargo	USA	225.0	0.0%
17	ABN Amro	Netherlands	217.4	-6.4%
18	Santander	UK	204.8	5.7%
19	Safra Sarasin Group	Switzerland	194.2	-8.9%
20	China Merchants Bank	China	192.9	57.7%
21	BNY Mellon	USA	191.8	0.4%

22	Credit Agricole	France	165.0	-3.7%
----	-----------------	--------	-------	-------

Continuation of the table 2

1	2	3	4	5
23	ICBC	China	154.1	28.8%
24	Lombard Odier	Switzerland	133.6	-1.7%
25	CIC	France	133.3	-1.2%

Source: Compiled by the author according to materials [10]

In 2015, most private banking institutions significantly slowed in growth of assets under management and reduced operating profit. Among the factors affecting the results were volatile markets, as well as customers hesitating to onboard business at levels previously experienced. The results show that industry is adjusting to turbulent financial headwinds.

The Swiss holding company UBS continues to be the leader of the industry. The top 25 experienced better efficiency ratios with a 75.1% cost-income ratio which is five points better than the all industry average of 80%. However, their total assets under management declined slightly more than other industry. Basically, this is due to the high volatility of the market, but at the same time it was influenced by the fact that many well-known firms carry undergoing restructures of their divisional reporting lines. Also, investment banks focused aggressively on improving their cost-effectiveness in their operating models in order to overcome the crisis in the industry and improve the competitiveness of their services.

Table 3. Key performance indicators for the global capital management industry

Key Performance Indicator	Average percentage of annual change		
	TOP 25 banks (2015)	All banks 2015	All banks 2014
Assets under management	-1.70%	-1.00%	2.00%
Net new money	33.00%	-6.90%	18.40%
Income	1.10%	0.50%	-4.30%
Expenses	-2.40%	1.40%	-5.20%
Operating profit	-4.70%	0.60%	9.30%
Cost / Income	75.10%	80.00%	81.40%
The involvement of wealthy clients (HNW)	68.6(100)	69.9(100)	69.2(100)

Source: Compiled by the author according to materials [10]

In recent years the development of digital technologies has influenced tremendously the financial sector in general and, in particular, private capital management.

FinTech rapid development

FinTech is a dynamic segment presented at the intersection of financial services and technology, where technological startups and new market participants use innovative approaches to products and services currently provided by the traditional financial services industry (fig. 2). Thanks to this, the FinTech segment is rapidly developing, breaking the usual order of things in the traditional value chain.

In fact, in 2015, the amount of funding for startups in the FinTech segment has more than doubled compared to the previous year, reaching 12.2 billion US dollars (in 2014 this figure was 5.6 billion US dollars).

According to recent researches [11, 12] the sector of asset management and private capital pays special attention to further enhancement of analytics of data for more effective detection and the quantitative assessment of risk.

Asset management and the private capital passes from physical consultations with technological support to consultations based on technologies with physical support. Also among key trends in private capital management are: the automatization of assets placement and capital flows control as well as the application of the advanced technologies allowing to realize investments in the new markets.

Development of robots-advisers for financial questions

Automated investment consultation (so-called "robots-consultants") presents serious competitive threat for operators at the market of investment services especially in a segment "only execution" and independent investments, however, it creates a challenge for traditional financial consultants. Such robotic and automated consulting resources will put pressure upon traditional consulting services and their price stimulating transformation process in consultation.

This change in financial consulting model creates difficulties for managing directors of private assets / capitals which many years worked on lining of mutually beneficial relations with clients with smaller volumes of assets. Robots consultants propose the cost-efficient solution for this segment, and on condition of their correct positioning as a part of the range of the offered services they can provide the soft junction to a complete complex of consulting services for clients with specific needs or with higher requests.

Fig. 2. Complex ecosystem of FinTech segment

Technology of a blockchain change rules of the game in branch of financial services

Blockchain is a new technology which integrates in itself a row of the mathematical, cryptography and economic principles allowing to message the database with an involvement of an unlimited number of users without the need for any check of the reliability or a check executed by the third-party organization. We assume that blockchain represents the next evolutionary stage in the field of technologies of a business process optimization.

On the other hand, though this technology really is very perspective, before its implementation it is necessary to solve several serious problems and to overcome a number of hindrances. Besides for deep understanding of technology of a blockchain and its commercial potential knowledge enveloping very different areas is required, and it carries to some uncertainty as regards concerns potential scopes of this technology.

Formation of online alternative finance market

Over the past several years, rapid developments in the global economic environment have pushed asset management to the forefront of social and economic change. According to the report of PWC [13], alternative firms, with their emphasis on investment outcomes rather than products, and specialization rather than commoditization, will increasingly attract investors seeking customization, diversification and genuine long-term alpha.

Indeed, online alternative finance has entered the mainstream, attracting growing numbers of consumers, entrepreneurial start-ups, established small businesses and institutional investors. Asia-Pacific shows the most outstanding performance reaching 221.7 bln EUR in 2016 (see table 4 below). Not surprisingly, alternative finance has also drawn the attention of large institutional investor and private capital managers.

Table 4. Alternative finance volumes by region (bln. EUR)

Region	Units	2013	2014	2015	2016	Average Compound Growth, %
Europe (incl. UK)	EUR (b)	1.13	2.83	5.43	7.67	90%
Americas (incl. US)	EUR (b)	3.24	9.65	29.98	31.81	114%
Asia-Pacific (inc. China)	EUR (b)	4.13	20.29	94.61	221.66	277%

Source: Compiled by the authors according to materials [14]

Thus, there are predictions that the principal focus for many firms will shift to creating a broader asset class and product mix and opening new distribution channels. While some firms still strive to become more institutionalised, the leading firms will work to build industrial-strength operational platforms. They will meet this challenge by revamping their business and infrastructure to be more agile and scalable, with a high degree of efficiency and operating leverage.

Conclusions

The world industry of private capital management is facing serious challenges, which are due, on the one hand, to global digital innovations, and on the other, to an increase in the level of competition, including from non-bank institutions.

We can distinguish the following new digital directions in the industry development: 1) automated investment consulting, 2) improving data analytics for more effective detection and quantification of risk, 3) inclusion of digital currencies in the investment portfolio, 4) development of alternative asset management (investments in online alternative finance market).

If traditional financial institutions set themselves the task of introducing new technologies into their existing architecture, they will be able to prepare themselves to act as executors of the main roles in the new financial services scene, where they will become the central link in the chain of work with the client and retain strong positions, even when the market undergoes changes under the influence of IT innovations. For successful competition, financial institutions will need to try to get the most out of what they have now. It's about trust from customers, brand awareness, access to data and knowledge of the regulatory environment.

References:

1. Markowitz, H. (1952). Portfolio selection // The Journal of Finance, 12(7), P. 77-91.
2. Smith, K. V. and M. B. Goudzwaard (1970). Survey of Investment Management: Teaching versus Practice // Journal of Finance, 25(2). – P. 329-347.
3. Merton, R. (2003): Thoughts on the Future: Theory and Practice in Investment Management // Financial Analysts Journal 59(1). – P. 17-23.
4. Maude D. (2006). Global Private Banking and Wealth Management: The New Realities // ISBN: 978-0-470-85421-1. – P. 360.
5. Molyneux Ph. and Omarini A. (1996): Private banking in Europe – getting clients and keeping them // Publisher: ICFAI University Press, Editors: B Sujatha, Nancy John, pp.166-197.
6. Aleksandrov, O. (2010). Private banking in Ukraine. Genesisexperience // Kiev. Publishing house "K.I.S." MMX. – P. 305.
7. Célérier C. and Vallée B. (2016). Catering to investors through product complexity // Working Paper Series. No 14 / June 2016. European Systemic Risk Board. – p. 43.
8. Yannick de Kerhor (2008): La mondialisation financière influence-t-elle les modes de gestion des entreprises ? // Géoéconomie. 2008/2 (n° 45). – pp.7-19.
8. Global Wealth 2016: Navigating the New Client Landscape. / Available at: <https://www.bcgperspectives.com/content/articles/financial-institutions-consumer-insight-global-wealth-2016/#chapter1>.
9. Scorpio Partnership Global Private Banking Benchmark 2016. Retrieved from <http://www.scorpiopartnership.com/press/new-normal-the-global-private-banking-industry-buffed-by-tough-market-conditions-with-many-seeing-aum-and-margin-dips>.
10. World overview of FinTech segment, March 2016. Blurring the boundaries: How companies of the FinTech segment influence the financial services sector/ Retrieved from <https://www.pwc.ru/ru/banking/publications/fintech-global-report-rus.pdf>.
11. Worldwealthreport 2016. Capgemini / Available at: www.worldwealthreport.com.
12. Alternative assetmanagement 2020: Fast forward to centre stage. Report. PWC. Retrieved from <https://www.pwc.com/jg/en/publications/alternative-asset-management-2020.pdf>.
13. Tania Ziegler, RotemShneor, Kieran Garvey, Karsten Wenzlaff, Nikos Yerole mou, Rui Hao, Bryan Zhang "Expanding Horizons: The 3rd European Alternative Finance Industry Report". 2016. p. 123. / Available at: https://www.jbs.cam.ac.uk/fileadmin/user_upload/research/centres/alternative-finance/downloads/2018-ccaf-exp-horizons.pdf.